

Emotional Intelligence as a Protective Moderator in the Association between Occupational Stress and Mental Health among Nursing Professionals

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Nursing Professionals operate in high-stress healthcare environments, with Indian nurses facing additional challenges such as heavy workloads, extended working hours, and inadequate institutional resources. Persistent occupational stress adversely affects mental health outcomes. Emotional Intelligence (EI) has been identified as a potential protective factor in stressful professional settings. The present study examined the moderating role of EI in the relationship between occupational stress and mental health among nursing staff. A sample of 304 nurses from six government and private healthcare institutions in Uttar Pradesh completed standardized measures of nursing stress, emotional intelligence, and mental health. Pearson's correlation and moderation analyses were conducted. Results indicated that occupational stress was negatively associated with both EI and mental health, while EI was positively related to mental health. Moderation analyses revealed that EI significantly buffered the adverse effects of stress on mental health. All four EI dimensions contributed to this effect, with perceiving and managing emotions demonstrating the strongest influence. These findings highlight EI as a critical resilience resource in high-stress healthcare environments.

Keywords: Occupational stress, mental health, emotional intelligence, nursing staff

Nursing staff are central to healthcare institutions; their duties include continuous patient care and complex clinical decision-making, making their role highly responsible and sensitive. However, the nursing profession is widely recognized as a top high-stress profession; they frequently face highly demanding situations, such as working long hours, heavy patient loads, exposure to patient suffering, a lack of proper resources, and quick response in emergency situation, etc. These frequently demanding and emotionally challenging situations are consistently linked to negative job outcomes and poor mental health, such as job dissatisfaction, burnout, anxiety, depression, and impaired psychological well-being (Ayed et al., 2014; Sarafis et al., 2016; Vernekar & Shah, 2018).

Since Menzies (1960) foundational work points out patient care, taking responsibility, decision making and organizational factors as core stressors, research has confirmed the persistent stressful nature of nursing. Excessive workload, low patient nurse ratio, limited autonomy, inadequate resources, insufficient administrative support, interpersonal conflicts, and workplace violence are some major factors that exacerbate stress among nurses worldwide (McGrath et

al., 2003; Lim et al., 2010; Roberts et al., 2012).

Researchers in the Indian sub-continent also explored stress levels and their negative effect in nursing staff. Bhatia et al. (2001) found that 87.4% of nursing staff reported experiencing a higher level of stress in their job. Even after two decades, researchers have consistently confirmed considerable high level of stress among Indian nursing staff. Singh et al. (2025) conducted a research study on 120 nurses in Indore and reported that 61% of nurses experience moderate-to-high occupational stress, while Kishore et al. (2020) who work in southern India, reported high psychological morbidity, health complains with 63.3% of nurses experiencing anxiety and 56.05% reporting depressive symptoms. Supporting these findings, in another study, Davey et al. (2019) observed that 77% of hospital nurses experienced a moderate-to-severe level of stress. Differences across healthcare settings have also been well documented. Sharma (2020) worked with 693 nurses of Uttarakhand and reported that nurses in government hospitals reported significantly elevated stress levels than those in private institutions. Bhadauria et al. (2025) specifically note that mental fatigue affects their ability to work efficiently and increases nursing errors by 30-50%.

Nursing professionals also exhibit elevated vulnerability to psychological distress as compared with the general population (Miranda, 2021) with substantial psychiatric morbidity documented (Kirkcaldy & Martin, 2000; Arafa et al., 2003). Identifying protective psychological factors is therefore critical.

Emotional Intelligence (EI), the ability to perceive, regulate, and utilize emotions (Mayer & Salovey, 1993) has emerged as a key resilient resource. Higher EI equips an individual to better cope, perceived lower level of stress, and improve mental health (Ciarrochi et al., 2000; Landa et al., 2008). Evidence further indicates that EI moderates the stress-mental health relationship among nursing staff, under high occupational stress, EI play

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buffering negative psychological outcomes (Barr, 2023; Molero-Jurado et al., 2019; Sharma et al., 2016). Szczygiel and Mikolajczak (2018) pointed out that managing and perceiving emotions are particularly important for stress resilience.

The persistent, high-demanding, and emotionally challenging situations inherent in nursing practice and the substantial psychological burden leads occupational stress. Examining the moderating role of EI in the occupational stress and mental health relationship is both theoretically and practically significant. Understanding this mechanism offers valuable insights for the development of the targeted EI-based interventions aimed at strengthening emotional competencies, promoting resilience, and nurturing sustainable mental health among nursing staff.

Objective of the Study

To examine the moderating role of Emotional Intelligence (EI) in the relationship between occupational stress and mental health among health workers.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There would be a significant relationship between occupational stress, mental health, and EI.
- EI will significantly moderate the relationship between occupational stress and mental health.
- The dimensions of EI will significantly moderate the relationship between occupational stress and mental health.

Method

Participants

The study included 304 health workers Nursing professionals, including 145 nurses from the public hospitals and 159 from the private hospitals. The sample consist 72 male and 232 female nursing professionals. The study was conducted on healthcare institutions of two districts of Uttar Pradesh - Varanasi and Lucknow. The inclusion criteria include registered nurses with a minimum of one year of professional experience and presently engaged in direct patient care.

Measures

Nursing Stress Scale (NSS): 34 items Nursing Stress Scale, measuring occupational stress in nurses developed by Gray-Toft and Anderson (1981). The NSS measures nursing staff occupational stress through seven subscales: Death and Dying, Workload, Conflict with Physicians, Lack of Support, Inadequate Preparation, Conflict with Other Nurses, and Uncertainty Concerning Treatment. Respondent rate the item on a Likert seven-point scale. The Cronbach's alpha was reported as 0.89, indicating a high reliability of the scale.

Multidimensional Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Scale-Revised (MSREIS-R): Developed by Pandey and Anand (2008) this scale is a brief, comprehensive measure of Emotional Intelligence. MSREIS includes four dimensions to measure EI: Perceiving Emotions, Expressing Emotions, Utilizing Emotions, and Managing Emotions. Responses are recorded on a Likert scale. The scale has been widely used in the Indian context and showed strong reliability.

Mental Health Questionnaire (MHQ): In the present study short version of MHQ consists of 27 items, which was validated and developed by Gupta and Singh (2018). The MHQ assess mental health of an individual through psychological, social, and emotional

well-being. Higher scores on MHQ indicate better mental health of the individual. Reliability of the scale is high, as Cronbach's alpha reported 0.896. MHQ has also been widely used by the Indian researchers across different sample.

Statistical Analysis

Correlational analyses were performed to find the relationships between the studied variables. Further, a moderation analysis was also conducted to test the proposed model.

Procedure

The study used convenience sampling to recruit nursing professionals from healthcare institutions. After obtaining informed consent, standardized psychological instruments were administered with clear instructions. Only willing participants were included. Completed questionnaires were scored according to manual guidelines. The data were coded, screened for accuracy, and entered into statistical software for analysis.

Results

Table 1

Relationship between Emotional Intelligence, Occupational Stress, and Mental Health

	Emotional Intelligence	Occupational Stress	Mental Health
Emotional Intelligence	–	-.413**	.692**
Occupational Stress		–	-.491**
Mean	192.91	101.95	72.66
SD	47.72	27.82	14.24

Note. $N=304, p<.01$

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics indicating that nurses reported emotional intelligence ($M = 192.91, SD = 47.72$), occupational stress ($M = 101.95, SD = 27.82$), and mental health ($M = 72.66, SD = 14.24$), indicating average levels with individual variability. Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient was also applied on data to examine the associations among emotional intelligence, occupational stress, and mental health. Emotional intelligence was negatively correlated with occupational stress, $r = -.413, p < .01$, and positively correlated with mental health, $r = .692, p < .01$. Occupational stress was negatively correlated with mental health, $r = -.491, p < .01$. These results indicate that higher emotional intelligence is related with lower occupational stress and better mental health, whereas higher occupational stress is correlated with poorer mental health.

Table 2

Relationship between Emotional Intelligence Dimensions, Occupational Stress, and Mental Health

	Mean	S.D.	Occupational Stress (r)	Mental Health (r)
Ability to perceive emotions	62.12	15.30	-.442**	.742**
Ability to utilize emotions	59.22	15.11	-.421**	.735**
Ability to express emotions	31.06	7.65	-.441**	.641**
Ability to manage emotions	37.98	9.12	-.195	.681**

Note. $N = 304, p < .01$

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the emotional

intelligence dimensions, including perceiving emotions ($M = 62.12$, $SD = 15.30$), utilizing emotions ($M = 59.22$, $SD = 15.11$), expressing emotions ($M = 31.06$, $SD = 7.65$), and managing emotions ($M = 37.98$, $SD = 9.12$). Pearson's correlation analysis highlights significant negative associations between occupational stress and three dimensions of emotional intelligence: ability to perceive emotions ($r = -.442$, $p < .01$), ability to utilize emotions ($r = -.421$, $p < .01$), and ability to express emotions ($r = -.441$, $p < .01$). The ability to manage emotions was weakly and non-significantly correlated with occupational stress ($r = -.195$, $p > .05$). In contrast, all the four

emotional intelligence dimensions highlights significant positive correlations with mental health, ranging from moderate to strong: perceiving emotions ($r = .742$, $p < .01$), utilizing emotions ($r = .745$, $p < .01$), expressing emotions ($r = .641$, $p < .01$), and managing emotions ($r = .681$, $p < .01$). These findings indicate that higher skills in perceiving, utilizing, and expressing emotions are linked to lower occupational stress, while all emotional intelligence dimensions are strongly associated with the better mental health among nursing professionals.

Table 3

Summary of Moderation Analysis for Emotional Intelligence (Dimensions) as a Moderator Variable in the Relationship between Occupational Stress and Mental Health

Model 1: Perceiving Emotions

Model summary: $R^2 = .532$, $F(3, 300) = 113.74$, $p < .001$

Predictor	β	SE	t	p	95% CI LL	95% CI UL
Constant	52.15	10.21	5.11	< .001	32.07	72.23
Occupational Stress	-0.57	0.08	-3.71	< .001	-0.44	-0.13
Perceiving Emotions	0.60	0.18	3.16	.002	0.21	0.91
Stress \times Perceiving Emotions	0.18	0.002	3.17	.002	0.002	0.010

Note. Standardized Beta (β) is reported in table

Model 2: Utilizing Emotions

Model summary: $R^2 = .535$, $F(3, 300) = 114.89$, $p < .001$

Predictor	β	SE	t	p	95% CI LL	95% CI UL
Constant	50.89	10.09	5.04	< .001	30.99	70.79
Occupational Stress	-0.57	0.08	-3.66	< .001	-0.44	-0.13
Utilizing Emotions	0.51	0.21	2.26	.025	0.06	0.90
Stress \times Utilizing Emotions	0.16	0.003	2.06	.040	0.000	0.012

Note. Standardized Beta (β) is reported in table

Model 3: Expressing Emotions

Model summary: $R^2 = .533$, $F(3, 300) = 113.83$, $p < .001$

Predictor	β	SE	t	p	95% CI LL	95% CI UL
Constant	54.73	10.35	5.29	< .001	34.38	75.08
Occupational Stress	-0.57	0.08	-3.67	< .001	-0.44	-0.13
Expressing Emotions	0.20	0.18	2.12	.035	0.03	0.73
Stress \times Expressing Emotions	0.08	0.002	2.36	.019	0.001	0.009

Note. Standardized Beta (β) is reported in table

Model 4: Managing Emotions

Model summary: $R^2 = .537$, $F(3, 300) = 116.09$, $p < .001$

Predictor	β	SE	t	p	95% CI LL	95% CI UL
Constant	49.96	9.92	5.04	< .001	30.43	69.49
Occupational Stress	-0.57	0.08	-3.69	< .001	-0.44	-0.13
Managing Emotions	0.41	0.20	3.24	.001	0.25	1.02
Stress \times Managing Emotions	0.14	0.002	3.57	< .001	0.004	0.012

Note. Standardized Beta (β) is reported in table

Table 3 presents the results of the moderation analyses to examine whether dimensions of Emotional Intelligence (EI) moderated the relationship between occupational stress and mental health among

nursing staff. All four models were statistically significant, explaining over 53% of the variance in the mental health outcomes (R^2 ranging from .532 to .537, $p < .001$). Occupational stress

consistently emerged as a significant adverse predictor of mental health across models ($\beta = -0.57, p < .001$), indicating that higher stress level was associated with poorer mental health. Each EI dimension showed a significant positive main effect on mental health, with perceiving emotions ($\beta = 0.60, p = .002$), utilizing emotions ($\beta = 0.51, p = .025$), expressing emotions ($\beta = 0.20, p = .035$), and managing emotions ($\beta = 0.41, p = .001$). Importantly, the interaction terms between occupational stress and each EI dimension were significant, confirming moderation effects. Specifically, perceiving emotions ($\beta = 0.08, p = .002$), utilizing emotions ($\beta = 0.16, p = .040$), expressing emotions ($\beta = 0.18, p = .019$), and managing emotions ($\beta = 0.14, p < .001$) each reduced the negative influence of occupational stress on mental health. Among these, managing emotions demonstrated the strongest buffering effect. Overall, the findings specify that higher emotional intelligence, particularly the ability to manage and perceive emotions, weakens the adverse influence of occupational stress on mental health among nursing staff.

Discussion

The results of the present study support prior researches indicating that EI functions as a protective factor in the association between occupational stress and mental health among nursing staff. Correlational analyses showed that EI was negatively related to occupational stress and positively related to mental health, suggesting that nurses with higher EI may cope more efficiently with workplace demands while maintaining well-being. Furthermore, moderation analyses also revealed that overall, EI and its dimensions attenuated the adverse impact of occupational stress on mental health, highlighting EI as an important psychological resource in high-pressure healthcare settings.

The findings are consistent with previous empirical research. Research by Landa et al. (2008), Newton et al. (2016), Karimi et al. (2015), and Ogińska-Bulik (2005) found that nursing staff with higher emotional intelligence had lower stress levels, supporting the idea that EI decreases vulnerability to professional strain.

Similarly, Görgens-Ekermans and Brand (2012) and Landa and Lopez (2010) found inverse associations between emotional control and occupational stress, highlighting the relevance of emotion regulation in stress management. (Karimi et al., 2014) Robbins et al. (2024) verified the moderating influence of EI in the link between occupational stress and psychological outcomes, which is consistent with the current study's findings that EI reduces the harmful influence of stress on mental health. Furthermore, Por et al. (2011) and Nikolaou and Tsaousis (2002) discovered that EI was favorably associated with mental health and adversely related to occupational stress, emphasizing the importance of emotional competencies in improving psychological health. The outcomes are consistent with the current study's evidence that EI reduces the unfavourable impact of stress on mental health.

The present study contributes to the existing literature by identifying specific dimensions of EI that are most strongly associated with resilience to occupational stress. In particular, emotional perception and emotional regulation emerged as significant moderators of the association between stress and mental health. This recommends that nurses who are able to accurately recognize emotions and regulate their emotional responses may

manage emotionally demanding clinical situations more effectively. These results have practical implications for professional development, indicating that training programs focusing on emotional awareness and emotion regulation skills can help reduce stress-related mental health risks among nursing staff. Overall, the results extend existing evidence by highlighting emotional intelligence as a central psychological resource that maintains mental health and enhances functioning in healthcare environments.

Conclusion

This study examined the moderating role of Emotional Intelligence (EI) in the relationship between occupational stress and mental health among nursing staff. Results of the study indicated that occupational stress is significantly and negatively connected with mental health, while EI serves both as a direct positive predictor of mental health and as a moderator that buffers the harmful effects of stress. Each EI dimension contributed to this protective effect, with the ability to perceive and manage emotions signifying the strongest influence.

These findings underscore that EI is a vital psychological resource in the nursing profession, enhancing overall mental health in high-demand clinical settings. In roles characterized by emotional work and high-stakes decision-making, the capacity to process, regulate, and apply emotions effectively lessens vulnerability to stress-related mental health problems.

Implications of the Study

The current study highlights how important EI is in reducing the negative impacts of work-related stress on nurses' mental health. These results imply that in order to improve nursing staff emotional control, empathy, and adaptive coping, healthcare organizations should implement EI-focused training and professional development initiatives. These kinds of programs can lessen burnout, improve work output, and improve patient care results. This protective effect was influenced by all aspects of EI, but the capacity to recognize and control emotions had the biggest impact.

The study contributes to the body of research on mental health in healthcare settings by empirically supporting EI as a moderating aspect in the association between stress and mental health. A healthy workplace may be promoted, psychological resilience may be strengthened, and susceptibility to stress-related diseases may be reduced by including EI enhancement into employee wellness and mental health programs.

Limitations and Future Research

The present study has several limitations. First, the sample was constrained to nursing professionals from selected hospitals, limiting generalizability to other settings. Second, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inferences, highlighting the necessity for longitudinal investigations. Third, reliance on self-report measures may introduce response biases; future research could incorporate objective or multi-source assessments. Additionally, while Emotional Intelligence was examined as a moderator, other factors such as coping strategies, social support, personality traits, and organizational context warrant exploration. Future researches should also consider workload, shift patterns, and institutional policies to better understand their interaction with EI in influencing mental health outcomes.

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